

Development of New Financial Content in the Context of Innovative Economic Development

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Abstract: *This article examines issues related to the development of new content of finance in the context of the development of financial science, the relationship between the state and finance in the process of the emergence and development of financial relations within the framework of the requirements of the New Uzbekistan and the strategy of innovative development of the economy.*

The article also systematically presents modern approaches to financial management and its elements, with special emphasis on incentive elements and shows their role and essential importance in ensuring final results while simultaneously reducing costs (expenses).

Keywords: *profit, modification of financial relations, situation, paradoxical thinking, costs, expenses, income, stimulators, innovative development, economic benefits, interest.*

Literature Review . The current exchange of opinions may unfold in the context of a radical economic reform. In the period preceding it, when the economy developed mainly on the basis of extensive growth, the financial relations preserved under the administrative-command system were used according to the following "traditional" scheme: society strives to interest enterprises with the difference between the reimbursed financial and monetary costs and the actual costs - profit; economic entities were reimbursed not any costs, but average costs, etc. In this case, profit acted as a stimulator of production operating at the enterprise level.

However, science must conduct its analysis from the position of not only the present, but also the future – that predominantly dynamic development of reproduction, to which market developing countries are rapidly moving. The problem of this article: does intensification not highlight the presence and development of essentially new moments in commodity-money relations, specific specifically to the market, without the recognition and proper use of which it can slow down? To answer this question, let us consider the contradictions that objectively arise between the processes of modification of financial relations, as well as possible forms of their resolution.

"Let's try on" our financial and economic relations to the ideal (100% economic growth). Of course, it is unlikely. But when considered "in its pure form" accepted in economic theory, the underlying dependencies become clearer. Having acted in this way, we find ourselves in the realm of views, paradoxes, uncertain situations and striking contradictions between essential processes and the movement of financial forms expressing these processes. Unfortunately, these situations or paradoxical views, the thinking of economists, for some reason, do not attract the attention of economists.

The first paradoxical thinking of economists . For intensive growth to be real, enterprises are obliged to achieve stabilization or reduction of newly created value ¹as an expression of labor time expenditure. At the same time, specific types of financial relations oblige the same enterprises to increase gross income in every possible way. With the growth of production, this goal must certainly be achieved, otherwise

¹ We are distracted from the increase in value due to the growth of intensity, complexity of labor, the creation of greater value by labor of exceptional productivity: all this does not cross out the paradox under consideration.

gross income will not stimulate production. An increase in gross income can be accompanied by financial stability or even a decrease in its real value. In other words, moving to the right, one must stubbornly go left on the compass of market-financial relations.

In the conditions of New Uzbekistan, the task of regulating the mechanism of financial support for innovative development of enterprises is becoming more urgent; of course, transparent mechanisms built within the framework of methods of financial stimulation of innovative development mean the disclosure of vulnerable bottlenecks, the development and implementation of more interesting, in our opinion, directions of innovative activity of economic entities.

If we proceed from the generally accepted position, then first of all attention is drawn to the need for good specialists who perform their professional functions more intelligently and are prepared for the urgent tasks of today, for the demands of the market - financiers, economists, managers who can regulate the financial mechanisms of management, planning and stimulation. Misunderstanding of the methods for solving the issues raised can certainly result in financial losses. Therefore, professional regulation of the volumes of funds intended for resource provision of innovative development requires the creation of a coherent system of financial relations. Errors in them can negate the advantages of new forms of relations, give rise to new disproportions in production. At the same time, not only to reveal the objective patterns of formation of quantitative methods, but also to show the entire process of their aggregation at different levels of management, planning and stimulation in order to reveal the influence of quantitative methods. The latter allows you to correctly assess situations in the process of resource distribution in order to obtain additional or synergistic profit.

The second paradoxical approach and its essential aspects are to a certain extent interconnected with the first. It is connected with the fact that according to this theoretical version the essential aspects of profit express in the broad sense of the word the costs of production. It is the monetary expression of the costs of the additional product.

In traditional theory, economic thinking presents us with the well-known truth that cost indicators are monetary expressions not so much of results as of enterprise costs, directly conditioned, giving the opportunity to advance the idea of recognizing the cost nature of the "shaft", where profit is an integral part, indirectly includes the recognition of the cost nature of profit. But almost no one speaks about this directly.

In a market economy, there is no universal dependence: the less the additional product, the worse. Let's say that the release of goods required A labor costs, including $0.5 A$ of additional labor. If the labor costs for the release became $0.5 A$, including an additional 0.25 , society would not lose, but win. Since enterprises are obliged to reduce labor costs during active growth, they must also limit their additional product costs. But financial relations (with traditional use) push enterprises to increase the monetary expression of the additional product (and part of the necessary one), labor costs - profit. The essence of intensification and its commodity-money forms "pull" in opposite directions here too.

The third paradoxical views express the possibility and significance essence and forms of manifestation of resource savings or, in the narrow sense, costs. At the essential level, absolute savings in material costs may remain unchanged, and savings directly on wages even contribute to a reduction in their size. But savings in material costs and wages can often result in an increase in profit. The latter can also change in the direction opposite to its essence - savings in labor costs.

the final result of all activities of enterprises with an innovative focus depends on how correctly and effectively the law-like connection is built. Similar versions can be continued. Will it be possible to manage the actual values of costs for innovative developments through prices, profits and other indicators that can determine the significance and effectiveness of innovative developments? The picture of the dynamics of actual monetary costs, which enterprises will have to follow, will also be distorted :

\$1 of costs on July 1 will be different from \$1 of costs on January 1 (actual labor costs are the same or lower, and in monetary terms they can grow). And this is in the context of innovative development, which requires a clear understanding of what is happening with costs at any given moment! Are we not receiving signals here about the lack of financial resources in traditional enterprises?

Although the above approaches are already noticeable, they can still be ignored with the prevalence of extensive development. Over time, they can create a contradiction, especially when using financial resources, even with intensive growth of enterprise indicators. If financial relations are understood traditionally (so that from year to year, in proportion to the growth of production, gross income and profit grow), the "indications" of market forms of management can diverge by 180 ° from the essential processes of innovative development. In such isolation from the deep processes, the use of market relations will, at the very least, create difficulties. On the other hand, if we "tie" the dynamics of gross income and profit to the essential dependencies of modernization, these forms of market relations would cease to be stimulators of innovative development of enterprises. A dead end results: it seems that neither the first nor the second is possible. In our opinion, the resolution of the contradiction - in the use of market relations, respectively, in essence, can lead to innovative development. Of course, stimulating the innovative development of enterprises that worked before innovative development will exhaust itself. But this does not mean either a rejection of market relations or innovative development. They must be used in other ways, new to our economy, subordination of the forms of these relations. In market relations, stimulators must be identified that interest enterprises in comprehensive modernization in order to create maximum conditions for innovative development, and at the same time adequately reflect its essential processes.

We may be objected: profit is a stimulator of innovative development, there is no need to look for other incentives, and we must tune in to activities under the conditions of the versions considered above. Therefore, let us look at profit not as a monetary expression of part of the costs, but as an indicator of stimulating innovation.

Let's say that last year the enterprise had \$15 million in profit, and this year it receives \$16 million. Is the entire profit of this year the result of the enterprise's efforts to produce innovative products in this year? Of course not. The "lion's" share of the profit the enterprise will receive is actually for repeating the production volumes, the indicators of previous years. It turns out that the enterprise's profit is, so to speak, "extensive-volume", due to the enterprise on the basis of the "gross" level already achieved in the past. In our example, only \$1 million of profit can be associated with the success of the innovation at the enterprise in this year.

The main economic benefits of innovation for the country are determined in the sphere of consumption. It is here that innovation frees up resources and makes production cheaper. The greater such cheapening, the higher the income, resources for increasing the production of goods, implementing economic and social programs of society. However, if we stick to reality, we have to admit: with the traditional use of financial relations, it is hardly possible to obtain the main benefits of intensification to the proper extent.

It is usually believed that profit always motivates the manufacturer to reduce costs in every possible way. But it is overlooked that profit in market-developed countries does not affect innovative development in isolation, but together with other factors, including competition, unemployment, etc., which do not exist under socialism. The main role among these factors is played by the spontaneously established price. It is unknown what it will be tomorrow, the day after tomorrow. As a result, the owners of capital (proprietors) are focused on getting all the profit at once from today's successes in innovative development, and not just a part of it. Due to the unpredictability of the price, delays in modernization and cost savings for the owners are truly "like death."

The situation with prices in our country and other market developing countries is fundamentally different. Of course, traditionally using the experience of foreign countries, pricing is "free" on the market without serious consequences for itself. There is no alternative here. However, from the standpoint of the future, comprehensive modernization, this, it would seem, the only correct decision limits its stimulation. There are still moments of interest of enterprises not only in high prices (the manufacturer is always ready to sell at a higher price), but also in high costs.

For successful functioning of enterprises, their business must be efficient. Therefore, ensuring the efficiency of innovative developing enterprises is of utmost importance. The efficiency of enterprises must also be increased by minimizing lost profits. Lost profits are profits lost due to failure to use opportunities. Lost profits are lost profits from failure to invest in improving other indicators of enterprises.

Analysis of the state of the problematic research . One of the reasons is an unpleasant but stubborn fact: in our economy, profit is established based on the actual costs of enterprises plus profit. However, many economists opposed such establishment of prices and profit. Despite this, pricing, by common consent, was carried out in exactly this way. There are authors who believe that this is now over. The leadership of the Ministry of Economy and Finance (again!) has clearly proclaimed a decisive refusal to build prices on the basis of actually accrued costs. But this has not been achieved. Touching upon this, economists note that at the initial stage of reform there is a need to calculate the real "price level", the inclusion of the "forecasting level" in it, "profitability" should be at a level that would ensure the process of "self-financing" ². Here, in our opinion, with this interpretation of "self-financing", "price", "cost", "norm" and "standards" we will not get a real financial result. With this interpretation of these financial levers, depreciation charges are not excluded from the composition of costs, as a result of which the volume of profit is artificially reduced and the real financial result from the economic activities of enterprises is reduced. This approach to determining the value of such indicators is still found in economic literature (referring to 2020-2023).

The words in brackets are, of course, rhetoric. The point is that not some, but the majority of enterprises (as in previous price revisions) will have to legalize their actual costs, formed over many years of cost - extensive development, and add to these costs a profit that allows for self-financing. At the same time, the authorities can hardly be blamed or brought into the discussion: they have no right to deprive a significant number of enterprises of the opportunity for self-financing . They (and all of us along with them) have nowhere to go. "Blame" objective relations - the inevitability of our prices following, alas, actual costs. They are, as it were, for "later", after enterprises have new prices that sanction the actual costs. It is clear that waving fists after a fight will not determine the situation around price changes. Then, paradoxically, such a reform may eliminate the dependence: more costs - higher prices - higher profit? None of the practical workers doubt that the next revision of prices will also be determined by this dependence, according to which the path to the highest possible profit is through high costs. Calculating a new price based on taking into account the increase in resource costs means giving a higher profit in this price (for tax payments, self-financing, etc.). Moreover, the moments of profit dependence not only on actual costs, so to speak, on average, but also on individual costs are preserved.

Firstly, this dependence is preserved in contract prices, the use of which will be expanded. The meaning of these prices is precisely in the reliance on individual costs (depending on which the enterprise receives profit). In practice, costs are often taken "with a reserve" - the press is replete with examples of inflated, and even extortionate contract prices. Secondly, as the modernization of enterprises deepens, more and more goods are produced by two or three, or even one enterprise. Thirdly, the individualization currently

² Problems of financial and credit relations in conditions of self-financing // Collection of scientific works. Ed. colleagues. In the composition of prof. Molyakova D.S., prof. Pesselya M.A. - M.: MFI, 1989.- 95 p.

taking place in determining the economic size of profit and its distribution between society and the enterprise also leads to an expansion of the individual price base. When the price is uniform for an industry or group of enterprises, an enterprise with less favorable conditions can receive a preferential incentive adequate to the standards (for example, by creating conditions for self-financing). But at the same time, we cannot deny that the standards are being adapted to actual conditions. It is theoretically condemned, but in fact it takes place in practice.³ Yes, in their basic features, a number of terms began to be used more than 60-70 years ago. Of course, no one is suggesting a return to the old administrative method of management. But it is equally obvious that the current economic system differs sharply from the pre-transition periods. But the terminological concepts noted have undoubtedly proven tenacious.

Economists even spoke about this or expressed their opinions even before the transition period.⁴ Touching upon this, Professor E.A. Voznesensky, studying the theory of finance in the system of economic sciences, noted: "... financial relations at the level of a specific subject, if they are aimed at the targeted distribution and use of financial resources, then the norms and standards serve as levers regulating the formation and use of funds of monetary resources of enterprises."⁵

Some economists propose to introduce a single standard for profit distribution⁶, other economists are dubious about the standard distribution of profit, believing that this will most likely lead to the ruin of hundreds or more enterprises. The supporters of this action forget about economic balance. Does the liquidation of unprofitable enterprises save the economy from general imbalance? It has long been established that it is impossible to achieve it based on the action of the law of value. For balance (i.e., the proper provision of public needs), for example, in the extractive industry, agriculture, even far from the most effective enterprises are necessary. To a certain extent, this applies to other industries, and it is in the interests of society to help enterprises necessary for the national economy, including with individual standards.

But with the individualization of standards, which we believe cannot be avoided, the "struggle" for favorable standards will continue, and there will be "winners" who receive a portion of the profit at their disposal, as if depending on the level of individual costs. As we see, the interest in high costs is supplemented by a certain lack of interest in reducing them.

Contradiction between stimulation and innovation. Modern innovation offers production new products with a reduction in production costs sometimes hundreds and thousands of times. How can enterprises accept such innovations? This is a potential reduction in the contract price, since when setting it, the enterprise must be guided by certain rules, i.e. this is a reduction in profit. Meanwhile, with self-financing, the achieved level of profit is more important than ever: it is already involved in the growth of costs for social needs, investments, etc. The enterprise cannot lose it! And the more effective the innovation, the more costs it saves, i.e. the more profitable it is for society, the more sharply the enterprise will reject it.

Thus, the level of profit is weakly connected with innovation: there are still moments of interest in high costs; there is a lack of interest in reducing costs. The combination of these factors is a tendency of

³ Awakening a person's interest in work // *Izvestia*. 1987. August 4.; Smirnov V.I., Vissarionov A.B., Sinelnikov S.G. Economic prospects: a new role in the economic mechanism. - M.: *Economica*, 10989.- 191 p.; Normative-resource planning method. / Comp.: V.B.Ermakov. - M.: *Rosagropromizdat*, 1990.- 192 p.

⁴ Voznesensky E.A. Finance as a value category. - M.: *Finance and Statistics*, 1985. - P. 124.

⁵ *Ibid.*, pp. 124-125.

⁶ *Ibid.*

"expensive" innovation, according to which enterprises strive to move to increasingly expensive products - at any cost and regardless of actual economic efficiency.⁷

The tendency of innovation becoming more expensive will be dismissed by those who wish to: there are many trends! But both the slowdown of socio-economic development and the phenomena of controversial risk, which can lead to a decline, have developed from trends. The danger of the trend under consideration is that it threatens the core of the innovation strategy: through the high cost of productive consumption, it reduces the growth of national income. Stimulating innovation turns out to be internally contradictory: price, profit, together with other forms of market-financial relations simultaneously stimulate innovation and discourage it. The contradiction seems hopeless, because, it would seem, everything has been done for the expanded use of market relations. It seems impossible to abolish individual pricing and completely switch to a market economy. But the contradiction must be resolved, the innovation strategy is irreconcilable with any inhibiting factors.

Suggestions and recommendations on the research topic.

How can contradictions be resolved? The contradiction of the system of "innovations and market relations" is investigated by the recognition that the new content of financial relations corresponds to a new subordination of price, profit and other forms of relations, their, one might say, different, non-traditional logic. First, we will show the decisive link of this logic using an example, and then draw general conclusions.

Enterprise "A" received huge profits from its activities : the cheapest raw materials in the country were taken from the surface. But society suffered losses: the pursuit of maximum profit, of tons, reduced the quality of raw materials, power plants could not operate normally, their expensive equipment failed, etc. In the conditions of the modern economy, the main source of savings for enterprises operating in such a "coupling" is the reduction of costs for electricity produced in accordance with the task. But how to "target" financial relations on this resource?

Firstly , both energy and raw materials producers should receive all economic incentive funds exclusively for reducing the costs of electricity production, i.e. for excess profit of this kind. Unlike traditional gross profit, excess profit is entirely determined by the success of innovation in the year in question.

Secondly , the priority theoretical and practical question is how to economically fix and express excess profit from innovation. It is not only a matter of the strict inadmissibility of padding (although this is also important). It is necessary to express excess profit in such a way that the reduction in labor costs corresponds to a reduction in their monetary expression (otherwise, over time, "Through the Looking Glass" will occur); so that society receives a reduction in the cost of productive consumption and an increase in income. All of the above is focused on the solution: power engineers convert excess profit into a reduction in selling prices for their products. Since settlements with consumers are made through a bank, the latter is able to document the total amount of real reduction in the cost of electricity, or economically confirmed excess profit actually received by the economy. By the way, the bank's document is the only one on which the entire system of economic incentives for investment under consideration is based. Padding is impossible: being self-financing (they must settle with suppliers, the budget, their employees), power plants cannot reduce selling prices beyond what excess profit allows. Based on the bank's standard document, they receive market compensation for economically confirmed excess profit.

⁷ In conditions of market self-financing... the diversity of benefits of an innovative product encourages getting rid of cheap ones in favor of expensive ones. Awakenning a person's interest in work .

Thirdly, raw materials producers must receive from energy companies a bank-certified receipt on the amount of economically confirmed excess profit (if several suppliers contributed to the savings, the enterprise that received the excess profit, within the limits of its amount, presents receipts to each of them). In accordance with the "price" of the receipt, raw materials producers can be determined (according to standards) the volumes of funds allocated for stimulation.

Fourthly, enterprises should not reduce selling prices at the expense of reducing profit. Gross profit may cease to be or serve as a stimulator of innovative development, and only excess profit can replace this role, but it is also no less necessary than before. It is important that profit ceases to be a disincentive for innovation, so that enterprises do not hinder cost reduction for the sake of its level. In order for this problem to be resolved, the level of profit in price should be fixed by the state and, moreover, the profit itself should be subordinated to it. Having "earned" the means of stimulation through innovation, the enterprise receives them from the owner of the profit.

We will not dwell on other components of the new subordination of market relations, conditioned by the needs of innovation. The meaning of the new logic is in the refusal to stimulate the difference between higher reimbursable (through prices) and actual costs, because in this case the focus of enterprises is inevitably on the level of reimbursable costs, so that enterprises strive in every way to "raise" this level and achieve this to the detriment of innovation. The new logic is in direct stimulation of the reduction of individual actual costs, and in such a way (through the reduction of its price by the enterprise itself) that aligns the actions of the enterprise with the essence of the innovation and transfers its achievements to the country. We will also pay attention to the fact that a number of the most important economic and social problems are being solved in a comprehensive manner.

This is a problem of the interest of suppliers and consumers in achieving common success. They are driven to join forces by economic benefit. The consumer is looking for a supplier with the most effective innovations: the more effective the latter, the higher the excess profit, and, therefore, the market reward. But it is also vitally important for the supplier how the product will "behave" during operation, whether it will provide the consumer with increased productivity, cost savings. Such a union of suppliers and consumers should become the factor that determines the fate of innovative development. At the same time, the most difficult problem of quality will receive an economic solution. Low-quality products with a low technical level become unacceptable, absurd for the manufacturer. The entire incentive system "works" on standards as if in "automatic mode" and can be computerized.

General conclusion:

No one has proven that the new content of the innovative economy should appear only in such a subordination of their forms that are characteristic of the preceding stages of market development. Moreover, changes in the logic of their forms cannot occur. At the first stage, the enterprise functioned, first of all, as an "organ" of a single state entity. The forms of economic existence of this entity (private property, predictability, etc.) are now changing very significantly. For example, we are all witnesses to fundamental changes in the subordination between administrative and economic methods of management. And if changes, including major ones, are inevitable in the manifestations of specific market relations, then why should the logic of market forms of relations remain the same in the future as it was 30 years ago? Why should more advanced market relations unilaterally adapt to administrative management?

Of course, the complementarity of directly state and market relations will be strengthened at both poles of the contradiction between them. Comprehensive modernization and innovative development require qualitative changes not only in directly social, but also in commodity-money relations. Only taking this circumstance into account can the latter be "forced" to work effectively in the conditions of an innovative economy, to their actual renewal. Failure to take this into account, I am sure, dooms a special theoretical

discussion (including the one currently underway on the pages of financial publications) to sterility, from the point of view of developing practically significant conclusions and recommendations.

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